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DUAL EDUCATION: FOREIGN EXPERIENCE AND PROSPECTS FOR ITS APPLICATION IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract

This article is devoted to the study of the possibilities of dual education in the current education system. In particular, the authors have revealed the prerequisites for creating dual education and the stages of its formation. Moreover, the article presents the outcomes of the comparative analysis of foreign practice in the application of dual education, as well as the prospects for using its elements under conditions of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: dual education, educational process, academic learning, internship, practice.

Currently when education is the most essential means of achieving success and a symbol of a person's social position, there is an active integration of all countries into the world education system. As it is known, the development rates of the education in all spheres of the country's life and its status in the international arena largely depend on the quality of education.

In today's Uzbekistan higher education is one of the most rapidly growing areas, since a strong state with an innovation-based market economy, a robust civil society, where all human rights and interests are ensured, cannot be built without creating a decent human resources potential. The training of highly qualified specialists in the most demanded professions with latest knowledge, critical thinking and proficiency in foreign languages is a paramount objective set by the government of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

An efficient solution to this problem requires the search for new approaches to the organization of the educational process, which main aim is to train educate qualified personnel demanded in the current labor market.

If the focus was on the individual development of the personality of each student in the effective organization of the educational process at the beginning of XXI century, nowadays the economy's need for qualified personnel required for the technological renewal of many industries dominates. In this regard, dual education contributes to the effective implementation of the interaction between the real sector and education.

Dual education is a type of education in which the theoretical part of the learning process takes place on the basis of an educational institution and the practical part is held at the workplace.

Enterprises place their orders to educational institutions for a specific number of specialists, as well as employers are engaged in working out the curriculum. Students do internships at the enterprise in combination with part-time education.

Germany is considered to be the ancestor of the system of dual education. The experience of this country serves as a model for the entire European Union. The German system of vocational education is distinguished by a developed institution of mentoring, practice-oriented training and the active participation of business in personnel training. Dual education in Germany is put in a strict legislative framework and is implemented with the help of chambers of commerce and industry and chambers of crafts.

One of the first statutory acts regulating the system of vocational education and training in Germany was the industrial code adopted in 1869. Compulsory education for minors was introduced in the North German lands with the aim of improving working skills and according to the first industrial code. Subsequent amendments to the educational process involved the chambers of qualified crafts, which were imposed with the responsibility of supervising vocational training [3]. Furthermore, already adopted under the pressure of the small business movement in 1897, the law regulating the activities of craftsmen became the basis of current legislation on the dual system of vocational education and training in Germany - the Law on Vocational Training. The document envisaged the qualifications of the lecturers, fixed a three-year apprenticeship system with an exam at the end, and a system of contracts extended to the entire handicraft sector. The law ordered the chambers and guilds to deal with issues of education, as well as examinations for apprentices and masters [2]. Thus, the adopted legislation laid down the basic principles of the dual corporate structure of vocational education and training in Germany.

It should be noted that on the cusp of XIX-XX centuries there was a gradual improvement in industry-based education in specialized educational institutions in Germany. Thus, in 1920 compulsory vocational training for commercial professions was introduced. However, the entire legislative framework in the field

of vocational education and training remained fragmented until a certain point. Under a single federal document, the Vocational Training Law, the various (regional) regulations were merged in 1969. The foundations of legislation laid down at the end of XIX century were supplemented by provisions on the participation of the government and trade unions in the implementation of the dual system of vocational education and training. Since then, there has been a constant update of legislation in this area. So, 229 out of 375 education-based regulations were gradually updated in the period 1969-1990, and in 2005 the Vocational Training Act was generally updated, meaning that the dual system of vocational education and training, which has a long tradition in Germany, is constantly being updated.

As a result, in Germany, the dual system of vocational education and training has become an integral part of the general education and training system. Students have several opportunities to acquire a professional qualification after graduation: in a full cycle vocational school; within the framework of the dual system of vocational education and training/secondary vocational school; at the University of Applied Sciences, which also provides the opportunity to study in a dual system or at a regular university. And many choose training according to the dual system, which usually lasts 3 years (36 months) [5]. After all, in addition to relevant skills, the student receives a remuneration paid by the company, which is about one third of the salary of a skilled worker. The dual system of vocational education and training has a high reputation in Germany also with employers, since all apprentices are actively involved in many daily work processes. In Germany, 25% of enterprises participate in it. Thanks to the dual form of education, the student not only receives a diploma of vocational education, but also undergoes a long-term paid practice at the enterprise. After graduation, students receive guaranteed jobs.

Currently dual education is being successfully implemented in the Republic of Kazakhstan, the state that is the closest neighbor of Uzbekistan. The system of dual education in Kazakhstan has been introduced for more than 10 years. Initially, it was introduced in colleges, and in 2016 it was launched in higher education institutions.

In Kazakhstan, educational programs for technical and vocational education using dual learning process provide for theoretical training in educational institutions and minimum sixty percent of industrial training, professional practice on the basis of an enterprise (organization).

From the 2021-2022 academic year the colleges of Kazakhstan have been granted academic independence. Now they themselves, together with employers, determine the content of academic curricula and the terms of the learning process.

Academic curricula in dual education enable students to obtain the qualifications required and get a job in a shorter time, and if necessary, return and obtain additional qualifications. In addition, now the period of study in the dual format will be counted towards the seniority of students. Thus college graduates will be able to find jobs with existing work experience.

Participants in dual education in Kazakhstan can be:

- 1) educational institutions implementing academic programs of technical and vocational, post-secondary education regardless of the form of ownership;
- 2) enterprises (organizations) regardless of the form of ownership;
- 3) a learner - student (a trainee).

In Kazakhstan the enterprise participates in the development of working curricula and academic curricula of an educational institution, as well as learning and teaching support kits. Colleges, together with employers, determine the content of educational programs based on professional standards and regional characteristics, fix the timing, amount of learning time and introduce additional academic subjects (professional modules) if necessary. Thus, employers in cooperation with educational institutions have the opportunity to independently regulate the content of academic curricula in compliance with the needs of a rapidly changing economy [8].

Introduction of dual education into the educational process of Uzbekistan has occurred relatively recently. In this regard the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers № 163 “On measures to organize dual education in the vocational education system” was adopted on March 29, 2021.

This Resolution provided for the organization of dual education from the 2021/2022 academic year in the vocational education system in compliance with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Education”, as well as in order to create broad opportunities to support the interest of young people in acquiring professions and specialties.

• In addition, the Regulation on the procedure for organizing dual training in the vocational education system was approved according to this Resolution. This Regulation envisages:

- organization of dual education and its stages;
- the order of the educational process and on-the-job training in dual education;
- determination of duties, rights and responsibilities of participants in dual education.

In reliance upon the study of foreign experience in the field of dual education, today its efficient implementation in the Republic of Uzbekistan is implemented within the framework of the following aspects:

- linking the learning process of an educational institution with the conditions of production at the enterprise (organization);
- organizing the practical part of training process at enterprises (organizations) and the theoretical part in educational institutions;
- enhancing investment attractiveness of the regions and improving the training of mid-level personnel with the account of the real needs of the economy;
- developing the formats and models of cooperation between enterprises (organizations) and educational institutions;
- developing the competencies in the implementation of educational programs in combination with the professional activities;

- improving the training program with the account of the requirements of employers and their technological innovations;
- financing implementation of training and educational programs;
- improving the forms and methods of industry-based cooperation between enterprises (organizations) and educational institutions;
- further expansion of the participation of enterprises (organizations) in the grading of alumni;
- meeting the needs of the population of different ages in acquiring qualifications in relevant professions (specialties).

It should be noted that the advantages of dual education are not only for students who can see with their own eyes how the theory works in practice. The dual education system becomes profitable for enterprises due to the following factors:

- personnel training is carried out for specific technological processes that exactly meet the requirements of the enterprise;
- increase in productivity, quality of services and products;
- reduction of terms of adaptation of alumni at the enterprise;
- achieving a greater return on invested capital as a result of their learning efforts in the long term;
- reduction of the cost of enhanced (extra) training.

In conclusion, it should be noted that successful implementation of dual education will contribute to the further integration of the educational process with practice and production. In addition, some activities will be organized to expand partnerships with leading specialized foreign research centres and educational institutions, optimize areas and specialties of education with

the account of the prospects for the integrated development of regions and sectors of the economy, the needs of ongoing territorial and cross-industry programs of the Republic of Uzbekistan

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